

1 **THERMAL NATURAL CONVECTION ANALYSIS OF OLIVE OIL IN**
2 **DIFFERENT COOKWARE MATERIALS FOR INDUCTION STOVES**

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8

9 **Abstract**

10 This manuscript describes the analysis of temperature and the distribution of natural
11 convection flow of three different cookware materials composed of stainless steel, aluminum
12 and enameled iron, when heating olive oil. A Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) software,
13 called COMSOL Multiphysics©, has been used to analyze the heat transfer process for this
14 study. In addition, a thermographic camera and a particle tracer were employed to compare
15 the measurements of temperature, heat transfer and flow velocity, obtained from the CFD
16 analysis. The results demonstrated that the enameled iron was the best choice of cookware
17 material for induction stoves, as with the increment of oil temperature, this material had the
18 biggest contrails and oil velocity convection flow in the center of the cookware.

19 **Keywords:** Induction heating, computational fluid dynamic, heat transfer
20 analysis, olive oil, cookware.

Nomenclature		Nomenclature	
\mathbf{u}	velocity of the field	\vec{H}	magnetic field (A/m)
p	pressure (N/m ²)	\vec{J}	electric current density (A/m ²)
F	volume Force	t	time (s)
ρ	density of the fluid (kg/m ³)	T	temperature (°C)
η	dynamic viscosity	\vec{B}	magnetic induction (N s/C m)
∇	vector differential operator	\vec{D}	electric flux density (C/m ²)
\vec{A}	magnetic vector potential (V s/m)	\vec{E}	electric field (V/m)
C_p	heat capacity of the fluid	Q	source term
ϵ_0	permittivity of vacuum	μ_0	permeability of vacuum
σ	electrical conductivity	N	number of turns of the coil
A	total cross area of the coil	I_{coil}	total current
\mathbf{u}	velocity field component in axis x	\mathbf{v}	velocity field component in axis y

21

22 1. INTRODUCTION

23 The Induction Heating (IH) principle in an induction stove works due to the alternating
24 current flow generated in the coil, which produces an alternating magnetic field that is
25 inducted on the ferromagnetic bottom of the cookware [1-3]. The increase of the induction
26 stoves demand at a household level, is because induction stoves have several advantages in
27 comparison to conventional liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) based stoves and electric coil
28 stoves [1-3]. The most important advantages are: i) energy efficiency, due to the reduction
29 of heating losses at households by the induced magnetic field in cookware; ii) enhanced
30 safety, there is no flame during cooking; iii) no waste of energy when cookware is removed

31 from the hob; iv) automatic cut-off function in case of overheating; v) no emission of harmful
32 fuel gasses; vi) easy to clean [1-3].

33 The use of induction stoves was promoted in Ecuador. The Ecuadorian government is
34 developing a world pioneer policy called “The national efficient cooking plan”, which aims
35 that 3 million LPG-based stoves migrate to induction stoves [4, 5]. In this way, the cookware
36 manufacturing industry needs a study, where different cookware materials are examined in
37 terms of better performance and results during heating a fluid and energy efficiency when
38 using induction stoves.

39 In food engineering, the Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) is applied to the numerical
40 solution of the Navier-Stokes Transport Equations, to show the results of the conservation of
41 mass and momentum, energy and state equations given by the initial and boundary conditions
42 of the computational domain [6-8]. CFD employed to improve the quality and safety of the
43 different food processing operations such as mixing, heating, drying, cooking, freezing,
44 pasteurization and sterilization relying on fluid flow [6-11]. The most significant studies
45 related to CFD in the food industry were summarized as follows. The thermal sterilization of
46 canned food in a 3-D pouch with CFD has been studied by Ghani et al. (2001) In [6]. CFD
47 for optimization in food processing for optimization in food engineering has been
48 investigated by Erdogdu (2009) In [8]. Hoang et al. (2000) made an analysis of the air flow
49 in a cold store by means of CFD In [10].

50 Understanding the thermal natural convection has become necessary in different branches
51 of science. Remarkably, during the last two decades great interest for food processing
52 applications has awoken [6-9]. With this purpose, numerical analysis and computational fluid
53 dynamic (CFD) software have been used by researchers, coupled with experimental

54 techniques of flow visualization, and temperature measurements [7]. Some of the CFD
55 applications to simulate convection flow are mentioned as follows. Kumar and Bhattacharya
56 (1991) analyzed the convection behavior, temperature change, and also change in airflow of
57 fluid foods during retort sterilization using CFD In [12]. The heat transfer in double-sided
58 cooking of meat patties considering two-dimensional geometry and radial 365 shrinkage has
59 been studied by Zorrilla, and Singh (2003) In [13]. The modelling of coupled heat and mass
60 transfer during a contact baking process has been investigated by Feyissa et al. (2011) In
61 [14]. Gandhi et al. (2011) studied the single and two-phase (boiling), natural convection,
62 accompanied by thermal stratification, using CFD simulations and Particle Image
63 Velocimetry (PIV) measurements In [7]. The inverse modeling of pan heating in domestic
64 cookers has been performed by Sanz-Serrano et al. (2016) In [15].

65 Regarding IH modeling, some studies have been conducted to understand the principles
66 of IH by numerical methods and CFD [16-19]. The numerical analysis of a new coil design
67 for induction heating and its experimental verification with globalization evaluation has been
68 performed by Kang et al. (2003) In [16]. Huang and Huang (2010) studied the effect of multi-
69 layered induction coils on efficiency and uniformity of surface heating, using multiple
70 physical coupling analyses in ANSYS software, to model the thermal effect of induction
71 heating on the surface of the heated target In [17]. The numerical optimization for induction
72 heat treatment processes has been analyzed by Naar and Bay (2013) In [18]. The numerical
73 analysis and thermographic behavior of induction heating, for this purpose they used
74 thermographic cameras in order to validate the temperature distribution and other dynamic
75 changes of a target surface has been investigated by Kranjc et al. (2007) In [19]. These

76 infrared measurements were obtained based on a color-coded thermal profile, and they
77 demonstrated to be useful tools to control cookware temperature distribution during IH [19].

78 This manuscript describes the analysis of temperature and the distribution of convection
79 flow of three different cookware materials composed of stainless steel, aluminum and
80 enameled iron, when heating oil in an induction stove. For this purpose, a computational fluid
81 dynamic (CFD) software COMSOL Multiphysics© has been employed, to analyze the heat
82 transfer process. In regard of the type of oil employed in this study, we observed that olive
83 oil maintains most of its nutritional properties during frying of different meals [20] and
84 therefore it has been selected for this study. In addition, a thermographic camera and particle
85 tracer have been used to compare the measurements of temperature, heat transfer, and flow
86 velocity, obtained from the CFD analysis.

87

88 **2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD**

89 **2.1 Experimental equipment**

90 The cookware was placed on an induction stove; model Mini Small Portable Induction
91 Cooktop stove SC-10B. This model has only one induction zone with a nominal power of
92 1000 W, a voltage of 110 V and nine power levels. The procedure of the performed tests
93 consisted in cookware heating with and without olive oil, within laboratory conditions of
94 15°C and 70% of humidity. In order to measure the temperatures on the base as well as on
95 the sides of the cookware, it used a thermographic camera, model FLUKE Ti125 that records
96 temperatures from -30°C to 385°C.

97 The cookware has been manufactured by UMCO, which is the biggest cookware industry
98 in Ecuador. The main characteristics of the cookware used in the tests are presented in Table

99 1. The thermophysical properties of the cookware have been given by UMCO which tested
100 them in the laboratories of Polytechnic National University of Quito [4, 21]. The first
101 cookware that was tested in this study is made out of enameled iron in its body and bottom;
102 the second cookware is made of AISI 304 stainless steel in its body and a three layer material
103 made of AISI 430 stainless steel, aluminum and iron in its base, all of them weld together to
104 the body. All lids are made of AISI 430 stainless steel layer. The body of the third cookware
105 tested, is made of aluminum, and the bottom of AISI 430 stainless steel. Hereafter the
106 cookware will be referred to as enameled iron, stainless steel and aluminum.

107 For these tests the cookware had different thickness. It is due that the enameled iron and
108 stainless steel cookware would weigh too much if they had the same thickness as the
109 aluminum pot. In the case of aluminum cookware, these would present problems in the
110 mechanical strength if they had the same thickness as the enameled iron and stainless steel
111 cookware [4, 22-24]. For this reason they have not been found cookware that have the same
112 thickness at its base with different cookware materials and it has been tested the commercial
113 cookware most similar in their geometrical characteristics.

Table 1 Geometrical and thermal characteristics of tested cookware

N°	Material of the body	Material of the bottom	Diameter of the bottom [m]	Diameter of the top [m]	Thickness of the body [m]	Thickness of bottom [m]	Height of the cookware [m]	Thermal conductivity of BM [$\frac{W}{m \cdot K}$]	Specific heat of the body [$\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$]	Density [Kg/m ³]	Thermal Diffusivity *10 ⁻⁵ [$\frac{m^2}{s}$]
1	Enameled iron	Enameled iron	0.16	0.20	0.0010	0.0010	0.07	53.3	500	7180	1.48
2	AISI 304 Stainless steel	AISI 430 Stainless steel	0.17	0.20	0.0012	0.0018	0.08	24.9	505	7800	0.63
3	Aluminum	AISI 430 Stainless steel	0.14	0.20	0.0020	0.0025	0.08	20.9	909	2700	0.85

116 2.2 Olive oil temperature and heat flux distribution measurements on the cookware

117 In order to measure the oil temperature on the cookware during the IH, a K-type
 118 thermocouple of 1 mm in diameter joined to a Fluke Multimeter 289 was used. The
 119 thermocouple endings have been submerged in the olive oil and placed at the center, half and
 120 border of the bottom. A volume of 0.5 L to perform the oil heating process was used for the
 121 study. The temperature and pressure never reached the boiling point during the test, so as to
 122 analyze the heating speed in each cookware and the natural convection of the oil distribution.
 123 The complex behavior of the oil phase changes has not been considered, to simplify the heat
 124 transfer model of the oil to a natural convection transfer process.

125 The surface temperature of the oil has been measured with an infrared thermometer, model
 126 W/ Laser Mastercool World Class Quality, 52224-A. Furthermore, two thermographic
 127 cameras model FLUKE Ti125 have been set, one of them in the front of the cookware with

128 a separation of 1.00 m. The second camera was set perpendicular at the base of the cookware
129 with a separation of 1.20 m. To achieve adequate temperature measures, the thermographic
130 cameras were set with an emissivity of 0.9, and at the same time these temperature measures
131 were contrasted with the infrared thermometer described earlier. Then, the induction stove
132 was turned on at the same time the thermographic cameras started recording the outstanding
133 temperature variations in a video, for this study. The cameras were able to record the
134 thermographs of the bottom and lateral sides of the cookware at different times, which has
135 allowed tagging the temperature distribution for several points of the cookware bottom.

136 The temperature analysis of the thermographic images at the sides and the bottom of the
137 cookware were performed during the heating and cooling process. Values of temperatures
138 were obtained every second; in the case of measuring the cookware without fluids, the
139 measurements were taken during five minutes, or until the temperature sensor of the
140 thermographic camera reached its limit of 385°C. In the case of measuring the cookware
141 with fluids, the measurements were recorded until the boiling point was reached.

142 The electromagnetic field analysis has been modeled using the COMSOL Multiphysics©
143 software, in order to obtain the heat distribution at the bottom of the cookware. To model the
144 heat generation distribution in the cookware, a three-dimensional finite element model has
145 been developed using the characteristics and properties of the induction stove and the
146 cookware materials. To simulate the electromagnetic field, a multi-turn coil from plane
147 copper coil, consisting of 22 wires of electrolytic copper and 0.5 mm of diameter was
148 employed. The materials and geometry of the coil was modeled in function of the datasheet
149 of the stove used in the test [6]. The temperature distribution and convection velocity have
150 been calculated joining the two Multiphysics modules at the same time [25, 26].

151 Once the heating test was finished, the stove was turned off and the temperature during
152 the cookware cooling period was measured. Measures were taken until the cookware central
153 zone reached a temperature of 65°C in the case of cookware without oil, and during five
154 minutes in the case of cookware with oil. The analyzed points were used to plot graphs of
155 temperature against time. The obtained temperature data were used to make a CFD analysis,
156 in order to obtain results related with convective heat flux, through the modulation and
157 simulation with the COMSOL Multiphysics© software.

158

159 **2.3. Visualization of convection flow in the cookware**

160 Particle tracers have been used for the visualization of olive oil flow in the cookware by
161 imitating the method for olive oil particle tracers [2], [27]. The particle tracer density has
162 been well-adjusted to the density of the olive oil (970 kg/m³). The particle tracer measured
163 0.0015 m of diameter. The tracer solution was exactly balanced to 5.8% isobutyl isopropyl
164 ether quantity.

165 **2.4. Physical model**

166 The cookware dimensions for the analytical model had 0.045 m in height, and had
167 different diameters as presented in Table 1. The volume of olive oil considered in the
168 cookware was equal to 0.5 L. To simulate the same conditions for this volume in the
169 experiment, the height of the olive oil on the cookware was 0.044 m. The thermophysical
170 properties of the olive oil as a function of the temperature are presented in Table 2 for the
171 simulation. The initial temperature was assumed as $T_{\text{outdoor}} = 15 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to start the simulation.

172

173

Table 2 Thermophysical properties considered by the olive oil [11]

Description	Units	Equation
Density	Kg/m ³	$\rho = 1098.29 - 0.60T - 1.55 \times 10^{-05} T^2$
Dynamic Viscosity	Pa s	$\eta = 117015.2 - 1844.98T + 11.64T^2 - 0.0367T^3 + 5.806 \times 10^{-05} T^4 - 3.67 \times 10^{-8} T^5$
Thermal expansion	1/K	$\alpha = 1.98 \times 10^{-04} + 6.08 \times 10^{-08} T + 7.04 \times 10^{-11} T^2$
Thermal conductivity	W/(m*K)	0.169 from 283 °K to 372 °K
Specific heat	J/(kg*K)	1999.477

174

175 2.5. Assumptions

176 In order to simplify the problem, the following assumptions have been made:

177 (1) Axi-symmetry: The cookware shape has been assumed as a cylinder. For this reason,
178 the convection flow shows axial symmetry due to the axi-symmetrical heating conditions.

179 (2) The heat generation due to viscous dissipation is negligible.

180 (3) The Boussinesq approximation has been applied for the buoyancy effect.

181 (4) No-slip conditions have been assumed at the inside cookware wall.

182 (5) Natural convection is assumed during the simulation, in as much as it was performed
183 below the olive oil boiling point. During the simulation laminar flow is conducted due to the
184 Rayleigh number $< 10^9$.

185 (6) The gravity force of 9.8 m/s² has been introduced axially to the cookware.

186

187 **2.6. Model equations**

188 • **Analysis of electromagnetic field**

189 The electromagnetic model was based on Maxwell equations. These equations allow the
190 calculation of heat through the base of the cookware with the electromagnetic field generated
191 by the coil; which is the input to solve the heat transfer equation as well as the fluid flow
192 equation. The heat generated in the cookware depends on three principal factors that are: the
193 electric current density, the distance between cookware and coil and the number of loops of
194 the coil. This system is based on the four following equations to calculate the effect of
195 electromagnetic field:

196

197 • **Magnetic flux**

198
$$\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \tag{1}$$

199 • **Maxwell – Gauss**

200
$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = 0 \tag{2}$$

201 • **Maxwell – Faraday**

202
$$\nabla \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \tag{3}$$

203 • **Maxwell – Ampere**

204
$$\nabla \times \vec{H} = \vec{J} + \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} \tag{4}$$

205 To obtain a closed system, the equations include constitutive relations that describe the
206 macroscopic properties of the medium. They are given as:

207
$$D = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r E \tag{5}$$

208
$$\mathbf{B} = \mu_o \mu_r \mathbf{H} \quad (6)$$

209
$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}_e \quad (7)$$

210 The equations can be formulated in differential form or integral form. The differential
211 form is presented here because it leads to differential equations that the finite element method
212 can handle. For general time-varying fields, **Maxwell and Ampere's law equation** can be
213 written in function of constitutive relations as:

214
$$(j\omega\sigma - \omega^2 \epsilon_o \epsilon_r) + \nabla \times (\mu_o^{-1} \mu_r^{-1} \mathbf{B}) - \sigma \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{J}_e \quad (8)$$

215 A Multi-Turn coil boundary condition was used in order to simulate the magnetic field, which
216 is generated by electric currents.

217
$$\mathbf{J}_e = \frac{NI_{coil}}{A} \quad (9)$$

218

219 **• Analysis of conjugate heat transfer.**

220 This model involved the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations from fluid dynamics
221 with a heat transfer equation. For this model, there were four unknown field variables
222 (dependent variables):

223 The incompressible Navier-Stokes equations consist of a momentum balance (a vector
224 equation), a mass conservation (10), and an incompressibility condition (11):

225

226
$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \rho \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{F} \quad (10)$$

227
$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (11)$$

228

229 The heat equation is an energy conservation equation that exposes that the change in
230 energy is equal to the heat source minus the divergence of the diffusive heat flux (12):

231

$$232 \quad \rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T \right) + \nabla \cdot (-k \nabla T) = Q \quad (12)$$

233

234 **2.7. Boundary conditions**

235 The boundary conditions to solve the physical model were:

236 a) Thermal insulation in the bottom because the cookware bottom was in contact with the
237 vitroceramic material of the stove, which has a low conductivity capacity. For this reason,
238 the heat loss through vitroceramic was negligible.

239 b) Use of convection heat flux boundary condition driven by the temperature difference
240 between the sides of the cookware wall and the surrounding atmosphere.

241 c) Use of convective heat flux boundary condition driven by the temperature difference
242 between the cookware and the olive oil. In the internal wall the flow speed was 0, and in the
243 external wall there was heat transfer between the inside cookware and environment.

244 d) The heat flux generated within the cookware bottom was set to **1000 W** which is the
245 power calculated in the induction heating analysis.

246 Boundary conditions for the cookware surface: ($r = R, z = 0$) were: $v_r = 0$; $v_\theta = 0$; $v_z = 0$

247 Olive oil temperature and initial velocity conditions were: $T = T_{ref} = 15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$;

248 $v_r = 0$; $v_\theta = 0$; $v_z = 0$ at $0 \leq r \leq R, 0 \leq h \leq H$

249 e) Volume force was used to simulate the effect of natural ventilation in olive oil. It was
250 changing during the heating process.

$$251 \quad F = -g * \rho (T, t) \quad (13)$$

252

253 **2.8. Solution strategy**

254 The convection flow of the olive oil in the cookware during IH has been simulated by
255 COMSOL Multiphysics© software which is based on the finite elements method. For this
256 purpose, the axi-symmetry and the calculation for only half of the cookware has been taken
257 into account. However, when convection occurred in the oil and air, the calculation has been
258 complex and lasted longer.

259 CFD was customized by COMSOL Multiphysics© programming to introduce the heat
260 generation into the CFD calculation by induced Eddy-current losses, or so called skin effect.
261 The high-frequency current or the electromagnetic field is limited to the surface of the
262 conductor. The measurements of the different cookware have been assumed.

263 The generated heat flux and temperature distributions within the bottom and in the axial
264 direction of the cookware was determined by the electromagnetic field analysis (EFA), for
265 the three different cookware materials as listed in **Figure 1**. Their values were used for the
266 CFD analysis by the COMSOL Multiphysics© module. In the case of the enameled iron and
267 the stainless steel, we observed that the heat distribution is similar and decreased in the center
268 and the side of the cookware.

269

270 **Figure 1** Generated heat flux distribution within the bottom of the cookware, with its body made of a) enameled iron, stainless
 271 steel, aluminum; where 0, on the horizontal axis, is the center of the cookware. b) Detail of the heat flux distribution for stainless
 272 steel, aluminum. c) Temperature distribution within the bottom of the cookware. The results have been determined by EFA.

274 The heat distribution decreases when getting close to the center and close to the side of
275 the cookware, like a doughnut shape. Meanwhile in the case of the aluminum body cookware,
276 the heat distribution decreases only when getting close to the lateral sides of the cookware.
277 In the case of the enameled iron cookware, the maximum value of heat flux detected reached
278 365000 W/m^2 , at 0.0475 m of the radius with respect to the center of the cookware. The
279 stainless steel cookware reached the highest values of heat flux of the three compared
280 cookware materials. In this material, the heat flux achieved 38500 W/m^2 at 0.0475 m of the
281 radius with respect to the center of the cookware. Whereas, the aluminum body cookware
282 presented maximum value of heat flux that reached 35000 W/m^2 , at 0.035 m of the radius,
283 with respect to the center of the cookware.

284 The cookware thickness is an important parameter to be considered when analyzing the
285 heat distribution in the cookware bottom [28, 29]. This parameter influences directly over
286 the induced current which is not uniform along the cookware bottom. As much as the
287 thickness increases, the current density decreases. Therefore, the thickness of skin effect
288 depends of induction frequency generated by the coil of the induction stove as well as the
289 electrical material properties like resistivity and permeability. In this layer 87% of the total
290 power has dissipated by the induction cooker. Thus, we can say that the heat transfer is
291 generated in this zone.

292 In this context, the enameled iron cookware as shown in Figure 1 c) has the highest
293 temperature distribution. This cookware has the least skin depth (0.04 mm) of all three
294 cookware that were analyzed. The cookware materials with aluminum and stainless steel
295 have the highest skin depth with 1 mm .

296 **2.9. Computational Grid**

297 To solve the differential equations used in the physical model, a free triangular mesh with
298 extra-fine resolution was built to ensure the model convergence as it can be observed in **Table**
299 3. The P2+P1 numerical discretization method is used, where the first number is the element
300 order for the fluid velocity, and the second number is the element order for the pressure. The
301 convergence criteria used in the simulation has two steps:

302 a) When the simulation started, a slight period of time was chosen, in order to **solve** the
303 model. Then, if the solution did not converge, it kept varying the time period until the solution
304 converged and the period of time was constant.

305 b) When the error was close to zero and it was constant during the simulation.

306

307 **Table 3** Mesh element size parameters

Element size parameters	
Maximum element size	0.0017 m
Minimum element size	6.38×10^{-6} m
Maximum element growth	1.2
Resolution of curvature	0.25
Resolution of narrow regions	1

308

309 The computational model to calculate the natural convection of olive oil heating has been
310 conducted for 400 s. The interval of time for each result was 0.01 s. For this purpose, 40000
311 steps were necessary. This computational model has required 18 h of cluster time on the

312 ENSIMS X3200 cluster of Dell Power Edge T620 (two CPUs speed 2.7 GHz), a RAM of 64
313 GB and a 24 processor core.

314

315 **3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

316 **3.1 Observation of temperature distribution with radiation thermometer**

317 The visualization of temperature distribution by thermographic images of the cookware
318 heated on the surface by IH after 15 s, for empty cookware, is shown in Figure 2. We
319 observed that in the enameled iron, the bottom of the cookware was heated in a doughnut
320 shape, just above the coil (Figure 2 a). This heated part rose to the highest temperature. In
321 the case of the stainless steel and aluminum cookware, the distribution of temperatures is
322 similar in all two bases (Figure 2 b) and c)). These results indicated that the higher heating
323 temperature for the inner base of enameled iron, with the same power selected of the cooker
324 should be correlated with a higher energy efficiency of the system cooker-cookware. For the
325 side of all three cookware, we observed that the bottom acquired a higher temperature,
326 because the cookware was empty (Figure 2 d) and f)). In the case of the enameled iron and
327 aluminum cookware, a hot zone due to high permeability of the first one and the heat
328 conductivity of the second one has been observed (Figure 2 f)). However, in the case of
329 stainless steel the smallest hot zone has been detected, due to the lower heat conductivity in
330 comparison to the aluminum material (Figure 2 e).

331 **Figure 2** Temperature distribution by a thermographic camera, images of the cookware heated on the surface by IH after 15
 332 s, for an empty cookware. Top view and side view for a), d) enameled iron, b), e) stainless steel, c), f) aluminum.

333 **3.2 Heat flux measurements**

334 The heat flux images from the cookware bottom with its body made of enameled iron,
 335 stainless steel and aluminum, during the heating process at 15 s, 30 s and 50 s are presented
 336 in **Figure 3**. When the temperature (**Figure 2**) and heat flux distributions (**Figure 3**) are
 337 compared a **similitude** between the results is revealed, and the boundary conditions in the
 338 case of IH are validated, which are directly related to the natural flow distributions. Results
 339 in **Figure 3** a) confirmed those results presented in **Figure 2** a), that are in relation to the
 340 doughnut shape for the temperature distribution of the enameled iron bottom cookware under

341 IH, when the heating time has been increased. A similar behavior appears in **Figure 3 b), c)**
342 for stainless steel and aluminum body cookware at 50 s of the heating time.

343 The heat transfer occurs in the contact area between the coil and the cookware bottom
344 surface, since this area is a small part of the whole area, a lot of power is required to extend
345 the heat to the entire area. For this reason, ferrite materials are commonly used for **their**
346 thermophysical properties. They are required to produce an influence into the magnetic field
347 concentration when given areas thereby refine the heat pattern produced. Emphasizing these
348 obtained results with an empty and with oil filled cookware. In this case, the fluid changed
349 the distribution of temperatures above the base.

350

351 **Figure 3** Heat flux results for the cookware bottom with its body made of a) enameled iron, b) stainless steel, c) aluminum,
352 during the heating process at 15 s, 30 s and 50 s.

353 In the case of the enameled iron cookware, the heat flux achieved a value of 54000 W/m^2
354 at 0.033 m from the center of the cookware and in 50 s of the heating process. Meanwhile in
355 the center of the cookware 27500 W/m^2 were achieved at the same time of the process (Figure
356 3 a). For the stainless steel cookware the heat flux achieved a peak value of 50500 W/m^2 at
357 0.007 m , from the center of the cookware and in 50 s of the heating process. In the center of
358 the cookware the stainless steel material achieved 20500 W/m^2 at 50 s of the heating process
359 (Figure 3 b). The stainless steel cookware the heat flux partially presented higher values on
360 left side than the right side of the Figure 3 b). It is due to the different configurations of the
361 material after machining presenting utensils [4, 21]. The aluminum body cookware heat flux
362 achieved a peak value of 55500 W/m^2 at 0.022 m from the center of the cookware in 50 s of
363 the heating process, meanwhile achieving 37500 W/m^2 in the center of the cookware at the
364 same time of the process (Figure 3 c).

365 The images of Figure 3 show as the heat flux incremented until a certain temperature and
366 time when it has been stabilized and it started to decrease. Kawakami et al. (2013) measured
367 that the heat flow started to decrease after the first 30 seconds of heating [2].

368 The distributions showed in Figure 3 depend on the thermal and magnetic material
369 properties of each cookware, as well as the material has a strong relationship with the
370 electromagnetic field generated in the base of the cookware. Although the same
371 electromagnetic field was applied to each cookware, the enameled iron material was heated
372 faster than the others, due to the materials higher thermal conductivity, which is how easily
373 the material absorbs and transmits energy.

374 Similar results have been reported by Kawakami et al. in [2] that are related with the
375 induced Eddy-currents losses, or so-called skin effect. The thermophysical properties such

376 as magnetic permeability and thermal conductivity **have** influence too. Magnetic
377 permeability has an influence into the magnetic field concentration and thermal conductivity
378 of the material that also has an influence into the conduction heat through the material (**Table**
379 1). In the case of stainless steel and aluminum cookware, heat flux and temperature
380 distribution **are similar** in the base due to the shape of the coils and the stationary induction
381 effect [2].

382

383 **3.3 Comparison **between** measured and calculated fluid temperature distribution in** 384 **the cookware.**

385 The contrast between the calculated temperature by COMSOL Multiphysics© and the
386 measured temperature in the border, half and center of the bottom for a stainless steel
387 cookware with **0.5 L** of olive oil, measured by the thermographic camera is presented in
388 **Figure 4**. As shown in **Figure 2 a)-c)**, the temperature along the base of the cookware was
389 almost constant. **Moreover, after 100 s of heating, an in-homogeneous distribution of the**
390 **convection may be happen in both cases. This irregular behavior could explain the higher**
391 **differences between the calculated and measured temperature change of the fluid in the pan**
392 **presented in Figure 4.** Differences have been observed between the COMSOL Multiphysics©
393 and measured temperatures at the initial stage, meanwhile, after 125 s, there was a correlation
394 between the temperature rate for COMSOL Multiphysics© and the experimental
395 measurements.

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Figure 4 Contrast between the calculated temperature by COMSOL Multiphysics© and the measured temperature in the border, half and center of the bottom for a stainless steel cookware with 0.5 L of olive oil measured by the thermographic camera.

3.4. Visualization of olive oil temperature distribution on the cookware

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The olive oil temperature distribution in the cookware heated for 300 s of all three cookware compositions are presented in **Figure 5**. As soon as the cookware was heated by IH, an increment in the temperature at the bottom of the cookware could be detected. The oil was heated along with the heating of the cookware bottom. In this case, part of the heated oil was rising until reaching the top oil surface after 300 s (**Figure 5**). In contrast of the cookware bottom visualization, without fluid (**Figure 2**), we observed that the temperature is homogeneous in the cookware bottom (**Figure 5**). In the case of enameled iron and the aluminum body cookware, the side temperatures did not rise significantly. While the stainless steel cookware presented the opposite behavior, since the sides of the cookware reached 170 °C at 0.04 m of height for the simulated heating time (**Figure 5**). The enameled iron, stainless steel and aluminum body cookware materials reached the highest temperature of about 257,8 °C. In the case of the enameled iron and aluminum body cookware the biggest contrails of

414 hotter fluid have been observed going from the bottom to the top (Figure 5 a), c)). This is due
 415 to their thermal and magnetic material properties such as magnetic permeability, specific heat
 416 and thermal conductivity. In case of enameled iron (Figure 5 a)) demonstrates how the
 417 density of contrails increased in the center of the cookware, and although these contrails were
 418 fewer, they were the biggest ones. In the case of the stainless steel cookware (Figure 5 c)),
 419 the highest number of contrails going to the top and dispersed by all the bottom area appear,
 420 but the contrails and the temperature of the fluid are lower than in the case of enameled iron
 421 and the aluminum body cookware.

422

423 **Figure 5** a) Olive oil temperature distribution in the cookware heated vs height and radius in 300 s for a) enameled iron, b)
 424 stainless steel and c) aluminum. The right extremity of the images is the side of the cookware, and the left extremity of the
 425 images is the center of the cookware.

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427 In addition, it has become clear that the oil near the bottom of the cookware received
428 higher IH in enameled iron and aluminum body cookware. It was due to their high magnetic
429 permeability and thermal conductivity, and the highest thermal diffusivity. Thermal
430 diffusivity is a property that indicates how fast the heat would be transferred through and out
431 of the material. Thermal diffusivity is the thermal conductivity divided by the heat capacity
432 unit (Table 1). Meanwhile, the liquid of the top was at the lowest temperature. It created a
433 buoyancy force due to the change in the density of the oil by different temperatures, which
434 generated a rising flow, from the bottom to the top of the cookware. The buoyancy-driven
435 flow induces recirculation zones in the oil. Therefore, the flow going up is turned to the
436 radially direction to the side of the cookware. In this position, the oil gets a lower temperature
437 and becomes heavier, which produces a downfall movement close to the bottom surface near
438 to the coil, which generates the movement again.

439

440 **3.5. Comparison between measured and calculated olive oil convection flow** 441 **distribution on the cookware.**

442 The visualization of the convection flow with tracer particles in the initial stage of IH for
443 enameled iron, stainless steel and aluminum are presented in Figure 6. The images have been
444 taken with a camera above the cookware every 2 s. We observed that the particles moved
445 from the center towards the outside wall of the cookware. The average speed v of the tracer
446 particles was calculated using $v = \sqrt{v_x^2 + v_y^2 + v_z^2}$. Flow velocity at the early stage and after
447 300 s of heating, for the different cookware are detailed in Table 4. We detected that
448 enameled iron cookware has the highest results of flow velocity at the early stage and after

449 300 s of heating. Furthermore, aluminum body cookware presented the best results of flow
 450 velocity than the stainless steel cookware.

451 The authors detected some errors by comparing the measured velocity to the modeled
 452 velocity. The average relative error for enameled iron was 35 %, 31 % for stainless steel and
 453 29 % for aluminum cookware. Some of the reported literature on CFD is in the percentage
 454 line of these errors. Kawakami et al. (2013) measured 33 % of error to predict the boiling
 455 water, and [2] reported an error range of 26 to 28.5%, in order to simulate the airflow pattern
 456 in a cold store. Mirade and Daudin (1998) In [11] presented an error of 40% when they
 457 studied the air flow pattern in a chiller with objects.

458

459 **Figure 6** Visualization of the convection flow with tracer particles in the initial stage of IH for a) enameled iron, b) stainless
 460 steel, c) aluminum. The tracer particles moved from color lines which are at a start and an end position. Images were
 461 overwritten every 2 s from 5 to 31 s of heating.

462 **Table 4** Flow velocity at the early stage and after 300 s of heating for enameled iron, stainless steel and
 463 aluminum body cookware.

Early stage of heating			At 300 s of heating		
enameled iron	stainless steel	aluminum	enameled iron	stainless steel	aluminum

Flow velocity (m/s)·10 ⁻⁶	5.4	4.2	4.8	2321	1027	2115
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465 The convection flow calculated with COMSOL Multiphysics© for the different cookware
466 materials heated by IH after 10, 60 and 300 s are presented in Figure 7. To compare the
467 changes in the convection flow for each time, it has kept the scales of the Figure 7 x.1 for all
468 images to 10 s, for Figure 7 x.2 for all images to 60 s and for Figure 7 x.3 for all images to
469 300 s. A correlation between the experimental measurements and the COMSOL
470 Multiphysics© values has been detected. The length of the arrow and the color of the scale
471 showed the magnitude of natural convection flow, while the scale of the images and the
472 direction of the arrow showed the direction of the convection. While the convection had
473 barely occurred at 10 s of the heating process, after 60 s the convection raised from the base
474 and the side of the cookware, especially in stainless steel as can be observed in Figure 7 b.2).
475 After 300 s the different patterns of the natural convection flow can be observed. In the case
476 of the enameled iron (Figure 7 a.3) the biggest contrails and natural convection flow in the
477 middle of the cookware can be detected. The tendency of convection from the inside to the
478 outside was strengthened after 300 s of heating. This is due to the thermophysical properties
479 such as high magnetic permeability, thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity. For the
480 stainless steel (Figure 7 b.3) the lowest contrails and natural convection flow was observed.
481 Whereas, at the aluminum body cookware (Figure 7 c.3) the contrails of the natural
482 convection flow dispersed by the oil into the cookware were clear for the viewers.

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b.1)

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b.2)

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b.3)

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c.1)

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c.2)

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c.3)

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495 **Fig. 7** Calculated natural convection flow in the cookware of a) enameled iron, b) stainless steel and c) aluminum after 10, 60
496 and 300 s. The right extremity of the figure is the side of the cookware, and the left extremity of the figure is the center of the
497 cookware.

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499 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

500 The performance of convection flow and temperature in different induction cookware
501 compositions such as stainless steel, aluminum and enameled iron during boiling olive oil
502 have been analyzed using COMSOL Multiphysics©. The results showed that COMSOL
503 Multiphysics© can accomplish the estimation of the convection flow of olive oil heated in
504 the cookware by IH. In addition, in order to compare the results of temperature, heat transfer
505 and flow velocity obtained from CFD analysis, experimental measurements of a
506 thermographic camera and a particle tracer have been performed as well.

507 The increment of the temperature rate in the experimental results correspond with the one
508 calculated by CFD. The biggest contrails of hotter fluid going from the bottom to the top
509 have been detected in the enameled iron and aluminum cookware. At the enameled iron
510 cookware material the density of contrails increased around the midpoint of the cookware.
511 In the case of stainless steel, the temperature of the fluid is lower than temperatures of the
512 other two cookware materials, but the number of contrails is higher.

513 While the convection had scarcely occurred at 10 s of heating, the convection increased
514 from the base and the lateral of the cookware after 60 s. Clearly different patterns of
515 convection flow velocity were observed after 300 s. At this time, the enameled iron presented
516 the biggest contrails and convection flow velocity in the middle of the cookware. This reason
517 and the increment of the temperature of the **fluid make** the enameled iron the best choice for
518 cookware material in induction stoves.

519 Magnetic permeability and thermal diffusivity are decisive for the choice the distribution
520 of material for the base of the pots. Magnetic permeability has influence into the magnetic
521 field concentration in the base of the cookware. Thermal diffusivity contributed in how fast
522 the heat would be transferred through and out of the material.

523 To conclude, this study contributes to the literature about CFD analysis and comparisons
524 with experimental models in fluids. This research helps to understand the thermal natural
525 convection of olive oil. It is the first research to evaluate the most suitable constitution of
526 cookware materials for induction stoves.

527 For future work, we recommend to perform the same analysis presented in this work, but
528 making a comparison between cookware of the same dimensions. It is responsibility of the
529 cookware producers to consider manufacturing cookware with similar dimensions that the
530 ones that are currently in the market.

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